

MONOTERPENOID. PART I. A SYNTHESIS OF ($\pm$)-CRYPTONE

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An improved procedure for the preparation of ($\pm$)-cryptone has been described. In an attempt to find an alternative route to this ketone, some interesting observations on the *tert.*-butyl chromate oxidation of a few alkylcyclohexenes have been made.

Cryptone or 4-isopropyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-one (III) was first described by Wallach (*Annalen*, 1905, 343, 30) as a degradation product of β -phellandrene. Later on it has been found to occur in Nature (Cahn *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1366; Berry *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 1448; Wienhaus and Striegler, Schimmel's Report, 1937, p. 91).

To us cryptone appeared to be a suitable starting material for a synthesis of cadinene, and with this end in view we have studied, as a first step, the preparation of ($\pm$)-cryptone. With the publication of a modification of the Birch reduction (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 430; *Quart. Rev.*, 1950, 4, 69) by Wilds and Nelson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5360), the previously studied route (Talukdar and Mukherji, *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 150; Bhati, *Curr. Sci.*, 1952, 21, 314) has been reinvestigated and a procedure developed for the preparation of cryptone.

Lithium and alcohol reduction of *p*-isopropylanisole in liquid ammonia afforded the corresponding dihydroanisole (I) in 90% yield; a small amount (9%) of a lower boiling fore-run, which had been identified as 1-isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (II), could also be isolated. The dihydro compound (I) was rather unstable; a seven-month old sample on redistillation yielded only 50% as the distillate, and this showed a maximum at 224 m μ , indicating that on storage some isomerisation to a conjugated isomer had taken place. The 2:5-dihydro-4-isopropylanisole (I) on treatment with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent furnished the corresponding derivative of cryptone in 87% yield. Similarly, the cryptone semicarbazone could be directly prepared from (I) in 78% yield. The regeneration of cryptone (III) from its semicarbazone has been described by Galloway, Dewar and Read (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1595) and Cooke and Macbeth (*ibid.*, 1938, 1408); the ketone could also be generated from its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone by Robinson's method (*Nature*, 1954, 173, 541), but the recovery was poor.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

* The experimental investigations embodying the results reported in the present paper were communicated to the Government of India in the form of a progress report of one of us (G.S.K.) on October 4, 1954. Also see Soffer and Jevnik, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 1002; Bhati, Ann. Rep. Indian Inst. of Science, Bangalore, 1954, p. 53.

Treatment of (I) with aqueous hydrochloric acid in dioxane afforded a ketonic material which from its n_D value (7.380) at $\lambda_{\max}$ (227 $m\mu$) indicated that the product was contaminated with the $\beta\gamma$ -isomer (IV) to the extent of about 40%. Filtration of this material through activated alumina (Basic/I) or its digestion with anhydrous oxalic acid in ethanol (Fieser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5421) did not shift the equilibrium in favour of the $\alpha\beta$ -isomer. A slight improvement in the cryptone content was achieved, when the product was treated according to the method of Barton *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 177f; Johnson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 1302). These experiments indicate that the direct preparation of pure cryptone from the enol-ether (I) is not feasible (cf. Birch, *ibid.*, 1946, 593).

The enol-ether (I) on treatment with Girard "P" reagent could be converted into the ketonic fractions to the extent of only 30%, and this material from the light absorption data was computed as an 1:1 mixture of (III) and (IV).

tert.-Butyl Chromate Oxidations

As an alternative to the above procedure for the synthesis of ($\pm$)-cryptone, the oxidation of 3-isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (V) by *tert.*-butyl chromate was investigated. This reagent has been shown (Oppenauer and Oberrauch, *Anales asoc. quim. Argentina*, 1949, 37, 240; *Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 44, 3871; Inhoffen *et al.*, *Chem. Ber.*, 1951, 84, 87; Heusler and Wettstein, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 25, 289; Dupont and Cow, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1953, 20, 60; Ezchinazi, *Perf. & Ess. Oil Rec.*, 1953, 44, 243) to be capable of oxidising an allylic methylene group to the corresponding carbonyl derivative. However, 3-isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene, instead of yielding the expected cryptone (III), furnished the isomeric $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone (VI). The structure of the product was confirmed by its light absorption data and a comparison of the melting points of the derivatives of the unsaturated (VI) and the corresponding reduced ketones. The fact that the starting material, as prepared by the method of Biggerstaff *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 934), was essentially (V), was established by its comparison with an authentic sample of 1-isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (II). It became apparent that the olefin (V) rearranged to the hydrocarbon (II) during the oxidation step; this was confirmed by carrying out the *tert.*-butyl chromate oxidation of 1-isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (II), when the same ketone (VI) could be isolated in about the same yield.

It is interesting to note that the *tert.*-butyl chromate attacked essentially the C_3 -methylene group, rather than the C_2 -position: this is in direct contrast to the attack by other allylic reagents which seek preferentially the carbon atom which is next to the more-substituted end of the ethylenic linkage (Mousseron *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1947, 224, 1062, 1230; Borgwardt and Schwenk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1185; Urien, *Compt. rend.*, 1934, 199, 363; Linstead, *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 34, 241). This preferential

attack by *tert*-butyl chromate was further borne out by the oxidation of 1-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene, when 3-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-one (VII) was isolated as the chief product of oxidation. This method of preparation of 3-alkyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-ones compares favourably with the previous methods (Mousseron and Winternitz, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1945, *v.* 12, 71; Woods *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2028; Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 593; Birch and Mukherji, *ibid.*, 1949, 2531) which involve many steps.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction of b.p. 40°-60°. All solvent extracts were finally dried over sodium sulphate. The light absorption measurements were carried out in 95% ethanol on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

p-isoPropylanisole was prepared by the methylation of *p*-isopropylphenol with dimethyl sulphate in alkali according to the directions of Bert (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1925, *iv*, 37, 1399); b.p. 104-105°/24 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5015, yield 93-97%.

Reduction of p-isoPropylanisole.—To a solution of *p*-isopropylanisole (15 g., 0.1 M) in dry ether (50 c.c.), placed in an one-litre three-necked flask, liquid ammonia (250 c.c.) was cautiously introduced under anhydrous conditions. The mixture was stirred and lithium pieces (4.6 g., 0.65 g. atom) were introduced during 10 minutes. Stirring was continued for another 10 minutes and then absolute ethanol (35 c.c.) was let in during 30 minutes with efficient stirring. The ammonia was allowed to evaporate off overnight and the residue carefully diluted with ice water (400 c.c.). The product was taken up in ether, washed with brine and dried. The solvent was stripped off and the residue (15 g.) precisely fractionated to give two cuts: (i) b.p. 55°-102°/23 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4600, yield 1.13 g. and (ii) b.p. 102-103°/23 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4765, yield 13.7 g.

The first fraction on rectification furnished a hydrocarbon (1.0 g.), b.p. 145°/684 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4585. This was identified as 1-isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (II) from a comparison of its physical properties with an authentic sample (*vide infra*) and the preparation of its nitrosochloride. A mixture of the hydrocarbon (0.4 g.), ethyl nitrite (0.5 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 c.c.) was well-chilled (ice-salt bath) and treated with HCl (A.R., 0.5 c.c.) during 5 minutes. The reaction mixture was stirred for 10 minutes more and left aside for 30 minutes, when a white crystalline solid (0.2 g.) separated. This was crystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture to afford white crystalline needles, m.p. 130°; mixed melting point with an authentic sample of the nitrosochloride, prepared as above from a sample of 1-isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (*vide infra*), was not depressed (Mallison, *Annalen*, 1908, 360, 69 reports m.p. 129°).

The second fraction represented the required 2:5-dihydro-4-isopropylanisole (I). A mixture of this product (1 g.), ethanol (70 c.c.), 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (1.3 g.) and HCl (conc., 1 c.c.) was refluxed for 5 minutes. After several hours at room temperature the crude cryptone 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (1.82 g., 87%), m.p. 126-31°, was collected. It was recrystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture as orange-red flakes, m.p. 135° (Gillespie and Macbeth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1332, report m.p. 130-131° for the *dl*-cryptone 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone). [Found: N, 17.7. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{18}O_4N_4$: N, 17.6 per cent].

A mixture of 2:5-dihydro-4-isopropylanisole (0.4 g.) was added to a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.5 g.) in water (2 c.c.) containing pyridine (0.2 c.c.); sufficient alcohol was added to just get a clear solution. This was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the crystalline material collected after allowing it to stand for 24 hours in a cooling chamber. The product (0.4 g., m.p. 174-78°) was recrystallised from ethanol as white plates of *cryptone semicarbazone*, m.p. 187° (Gillespie and Macbeth, *loc.cit.*, report m.p. 188°).

For the preparation of the above derivatives in good yield, it is necessary to use the 2:5-dihydro-4-isopropylanisole immediately after its preparation. A seven-month old sample after distillation had b.p. 105-107°/25 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4770; λ_{max} 224 m μ (ϵ , 5500).

Regeneration of Cryptone from its 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone.—The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (1.0 g.) was heated on the steam-bath with formic acid (90%, 8 c.c.) for one hour and then the acid was neutralised by the portion-wise addition of copper carbonate (12 g., 30 minutes). The product was then diluted with water and steam-distilled. The steam-distillate (100 c.c.) was extracted with ether (10 c.c. $\times$ 3), washed with brine and dried. The solvent was removed, when a pale yellow residue (0.15 g.), b.p. 110°/24 mm. was left. This immediately yielded the cryptone 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone on treatment with the reagent.

Hydrolysis of 2:5-Dihydro-4-isopropylanisole (I).—To a solution of the enol-ether (1 g.) in dioxane (pure, 30 c.c.) HCl (6 N, 3.4 c.c.) was added and maintained at 10° $\pm$ 2° with stirring for 2 hours. This was diluted with water (120 c.c.) and extracted with ether (10 c.c. $\times$ 4). The combined extracts were washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10%, 20 c.c.), brine (10 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated to yield a colorless liquid, b.p. 110°/24 mm., n_D^{27} 1.4750, yield 0.46 g. (50%). Light absorption: λ_{max} 227 m μ (ϵ , 7380) (Cooke and Macbeth, *loc.cit.*, report λ_{max}^{1500} 226.3 m μ , ϵ 12,590 for pure *l*-cryptone).

The above product (0.3 g.) in chloroform (4 c.c.) was treated with dry HCl gas for 1 hour at 0° (Barton *et al.*, *loc.cit.*). On working up as usual (Johnson *et al.*, *loc.cit.*), colorless distillate (0.2 g.) was obtained, b.p. 110°/24 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4790, λ_{max} 227 m μ (ϵ 8160).

A mixture of the enol-ether (I, 1.52 g.), alcohol (10 c.c.), glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.) and Girard reagent "P" (2 g.) was refluxed for 1½ hours. The product was worked up as described by Sterrett (Guenther, "The Essential Oils", D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New York, 1949, Vol. II, p. 816) by pouring into ice water (130 c.c.) containing sodium carbonate (0.8 g.). After removal of the non-ketonic material (apparently the starting enol-ether; 0.7 g., b.p. 102°/24 mm.) with ether, the clear aqueous part was treated with dilute sulphuric acid (20%, 3 c.c.) and after 2 hours at room temperature it was worked up by extraction with ether to yield a ketonic material (0.45 g.), b.p. 105°/24 mm., $n_D^{27.5}$ 1.4730, λ_{max} 227 m μ (ϵ , 6510).

3-isoPropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (V) was prepared essentially by the method of Biggerstaff *et al.* (*loc.cit.*), but the yields in our hands were superior. To a refluxing solution of 3-bromocyclohexene (22.4 g., Zeigler *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1942, 561, 80) in dry ether (30 c.c.) was added a solution of isopropylmagnesium bromide (from Mg 6.4 g., isopropyl bromide 40 g. and ether 100 c.c.) during one hour. The refluxing was continued for

another 2 hours and the reaction mixture left aside overnight. This was then treated with a solution of ammonium chloride (20 g.) in water (50 c.c.) during 30 minutes with stirring. The solvent layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (20 c.c. $\times$ 3). The combined extracts were washed with brine and dried. The solvent was removed (column) and the residue fractionated to yield the desired product as a colorless liquid, b.p. 88-90°/100 mm., n_D^{22} 1.4555, yield 11.8 g. (70%).

The *nitrosochloride* was prepared, as described above, for the isomeric hydrocarbon (II). The product on recrystallisation from benzene-alcohol mixture came out as fine white needles, m.p. 155°. (Found: N, 7.1. $C_9H_{10}ONCl$ requires N, 7.38 per cent).

3-isoPropyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-one (VI): (i) From *3-isoPropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene* (V).—*tert.*-Butyl chromate solution was prepared from chromic anhydride (16 g., 0.16 M), anhydrous *tert.*-butanol (44 c.c.) and CCl_4 (124 c.c.) according to the direction of Heusler and Wettstein (*loc. cit.*). The solution was concentrated to 84 c.c. and then diluted with glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.). This reagent was added to the above hydrocarbon (5 g., 0.04 M) in dry CCl_4 (28 c.c.) during 45 minutes at 70°-75° with stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred at this temperature for another, 2½ hours and then the green product left aside overnight. To this, aqueous oxalic acid (16 g. in 160 c.c. of water) was let in during one hour with stirring at room temperature; this was followed by the addition of solid oxalic acid (12 g.) during 15 minutes. The pale yellow CCl_4 layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with CCl_4 (20 c.c. $\times$ 3). The combined solvent layers were washed neutral with water (20 c.c.), aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10%, 40 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried. The solvent was flashed off and the pale yellow residue filtered through a column of activated alumina (Basic/1; 30 g.); this was washed with petroleum ether (180 c.c.). This treatment left the coloured impurity as a violet-green band on the column. The almost colorless petroleum ether eluate was distilled (column) to remove the solvent; the residue was fractionated to yield a colorless liquid, b.p. 112-13°/20 mm., $n_D^{27.5}$ 1.4845, yield 2.1-2.4 g. Light absorption: λ_{max} 235 m μ (ϵ , 10,000) (Woods *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 59-60°/0.3 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4842; cf. Roy, *Science & Culture*, 1953, 19, 156).

The crude 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method), m.p. 138°-145°, was obtained in 80% yield. Recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether mixture furnished scarlet-red prisms, m.p. 154-55° (Woods *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 154.4°-155.5°).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared by the pyridine method and after three crystallisations from ethanol furnished white plates, m.p. 184° (Woods *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 179-179.5°). A mixed melting point determination with ($\pm$)-cryptone semicarbazone gave a sharp depression.

When the unsaturated ketone (1 g.) in ethanol (12 c.c.) was hydrogenated in the presence of pre-reduced Pd-CaCO₃ catalyst (0.5 g., 5%), hydrogen equivalent to one ethylenic linkage was readily (15 minutes) taken up, and the reduction came to a close. The reduced material was worked up in the usual manner to yield *3-isopropylcyclohexanone* as a colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 200°-205°/684 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4560 (Woods *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 50-51°/1 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4540). Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone

(HCl method) was obtained as golden yellow flakes from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 139° (Woods *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 139-40°). The semicarbazone was obtained as white leaflets on two crystallisations from ethanol, m.p. 190° (Woods *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 194.5-95°; Whitmore and Pedlow, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 758, record m.p. 189-90°).

(ii) *From 1-isoPropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (II).*—The hydrocarbon was prepared by the action of isopropylmagnesium bromide on cyclohexanone and subsequent dehydration of the carbinol with a trace of iodine (Mosher, *ibid.*, 1940, 62, 552). The material had b.p. 145°/684 mm., n_D^{26} 1.4590 (Mallison, *loc. cit.*, record n_D^{50} 1.4606) and afforded a nitrosochloride, m.p. 129-130°, prepared as described above.

The olefin (1.98 g., 0.016 M) was oxidised with *tert.*-butyl chromate reagent as described above for (V). The purified ketone (VI), b.p. 112-15°/22 mm., $n_D^{27.5}$ 1.4850, was obtained in 40% yield. The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 155°, and the semicarbazone, m.p. 183-84°, did not depress the melting points of the corresponding derivatives of the ketone (VI), obtained from the 3-*isopropyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (V)*.

Oxidation of Methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene: Isolation of 3-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexen-1-one.—When Δ^1 -methylcyclohexene (3.8 g., 0.04 M) was oxidised with *tert.*-butyl chromate reagent, as described for (V), the unsaturated ketone was isolated in 25% yield as a colorless liquid, b.p. 100°-104°/30 mm., n_D^{28} 1.4840; 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, bright red prisms (benzene), m.p. 178°; semicarbazone, white prisms (pyridine-ethanol method; crystallised from ethanol), m.p. 201° (Woods *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 40°/0.8 mm., n_D^{30} 1.4945; 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 177-78°; semicarbazone, m.p. 198.5-99.5°).

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